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Theoretical Foundations of Teaching Arabic Speech Activities

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***Abstract:** This article examines the theoretical foundations of teaching Arabic language speaking skills. It analyzes three approaches to foreign language teaching: direct methods, conscious (translation) methods, and combined methods. The perspectives of proponents of each of these three methods are examined.*

***Key words:** Arabic language, lesson, pedagogical technology, technology, method.*

The process of globalization of life and culture is expanding and deepening, and therefore, in particular, each national culture in the world is a constantly changing element of a single world culture.

Language plays a huge role in preserving and developing the spiritual and material values of each nation. The demands for foreign language teaching are constantly increasing. By mastering a language, a person simultaneously penetrates into a new national culture and gains access to the immense wealth stored in that language.

Teaching methodology is an integral component and one of the core academic disciplines in the study of literary Arabic within educational institutions. Knowledge of Arabic language teaching methodology is essential for future foreign language teachers. Currently, there is an acute shortage of teaching materials dedicated to the methodology of teaching Arabic.

Arabic belongs to the Semitic language family and is the official language of twenty-two countries in the Arabian Peninsula, North Africa, and the Middle East. Each of the Arab countries has its own unique characteristics: economy, government, geography, history, culture, education, national traditions, dialects, and so on. Therefore, the study of Arab countries and the Arabic language can be considered separate disciplines in terms of content structure and the philological training of future specialists. Ibn Khaldun, the most prominent representative of the Hispano-Maghrebian school of thought, in his historical and philosophical treatise "Muqaddimah," drew attention to the particular

difficulty of perceiving and learning the Arabic language for foreigners: "For those who are farthest removed from using the Arabic language, its acquisition is most difficult"¹.

However, an analysis of the theory and practice of contemporary Arabic language teaching in domestic educational institutions at the present stage has shown that the learning process is primarily oriented towards the development of students' memory, whereas modern pedagogy emphasizes the development of thinking and the activation of cognitive activity. The ability to think not only in one's native language but also in a foreign language is invaluable in the context of globalization, tolerance, and the national identity of society and the individual.

The primary communicative goal of teaching Arabic is to develop communicative competence. Speech activities (listening, speaking, reading, writing) are one of the main aspects of learning Arabic. They are essential for the development of self-study materials in Arabic.

The methods chosen by teachers play a crucial role in foreign language teaching. According to M.I. Makhmoutov, "a teaching method is a system of rules for pedagogical interaction, conditioned by the principles of teaching, which the teacher and students use as a guide in selecting techniques and methods of specific actions leading to the achievement of a particular goal"². A teaching method reflects a specific type of interaction between the activities of the teacher and the students, a certain combination of teaching and learning methods that allows students to successfully acquire knowledge and skills, apply them in practice, and develop cognitive abilities and independence³.

The following groups of foreign language teaching methods are distinguished: 1) direct; 2) conscious (translation); 3) combined.

Characteristics of the direct method:

The native language is excluded from the learning process.

The main emphasis is placed on teaching oral speech through the intuitive acquisition of the language.

Reading and writing are merely means of consolidating learned foreign words and phrases.

Grammar and translation are relegated to a secondary role.

The proponents of the direct method in Russia in the 1920s included E.A. Fekhner, K.A. Ganshina, D. Shestakov, E.I. Spendiarov, and others. N.K. Krupskaya commented on the direct method as follows: "The easiest way to learn a language is through communication. The best means of initial language learning would be widespread communication between children speaking different languages"⁴. The purpose of such a method is precisely to make learning as similar to communication as possible.

According to T.A. Shaikhullin, this method has the following advantages:

Practical orientation of learning (acquiring skills in the target language).

Increased student motivation due to the approximation to the surrounding real environment.

Exclusion of interference from the native language. However, the author believes that the direct method has serious drawbacks:

¹ Basiyeva S.M. Istoriko-sosiologicheskiy traktat Ibn Xalduna «Mukaddima». – M., 1965. – P.138

² Maxmutov M.I. Sovremenniy urok: Voprosi teorii. - M.: Pedagogika, 1985. – P.41

³ Maxmutov M.I. Problemnoye obucheniye. Osnovniye voprosi teorii. M., Pedagogika, 1975. – P.308.

⁴ Kudryavsev T.V. Logiko-psixologicheskiye osnovi stanovleniya mishleniya v obuchenii //Razvivayushyeye obucheniye. Tom 1. Dialog s V.V. Davidovim. - M.: APK i PRO, 2002. - P. 70.

It does not ensure in-depth language learning due to the exclusion of grammar and translation.

It does not adequately ensure accurate understanding of foreign words (especially abstract concepts).

The role of educational texts is underestimated, as the focus shifts to spoken language⁵.

2. The conscious-comparative method involves paying significant attention to translation. For example, E.K. Chapliya argued that "translation is the most effective way of assimilating linguistic material and a means of consciously comparing the structures of two languages"⁶. I.V. Rakhmanov argued that "since thoughts exist only on the basis of linguistic material, and learners think in their native language, the only means of understanding what is read or heard is translation into the native language, either aloud or silently"⁷.

Thus, the main characteristics of the conscious-comparative method of foreign language learning are:

- Comparison with the native language.
- A strong emphasis on grammar and theoretical explanations.
- A focus on teaching reading and translation (direct, reverse, oral, written).

The positive aspects of this method are:

1. A precise understanding of words and expressions in the target language by learners.
 2. A significant focus on working with учебные тексты (educational texts).
 3. In our view, this method has a number of drawbacks:
 4. Learners' attention is divided between their native language and the target language, with more attention being focused on the familiar native language. It seems to us that learners' understanding is primarily achieved through the use of their native language.
 5. An overemphasis on grammar and excessive theorizing.
- Insufficient attention to the teaching of spoken language.

3. The combined method involves a broad introduction to the target language, including its spoken language, reading, writing, and grammar. Using the combined method, learners acquire communicative competence, that is, the ability and willingness to engage in foreign language communication.

The trend of teaching foreign languages as a second language through real or simulated speaking, listening, reading, and writing has become dominant in language teaching. Therefore, some researchers, such as M.L. Weissburd, believe that the activity-based, personality-oriented, communicative approach is the primary method of foreign language teaching in our time.

In Russian language didactics, the theoretical foundations of the communicative approach to foreign language teaching were first outlined by E.I. Passov in 1977. He is rightfully considered the founder of this approach in Russia. Representatives of the Lipetsk methodological school, such as E.I. Passov,

⁵Shayxullin T.A., Gazal Ainiya A.N., Obucheniye rechevoy deyatelnosti arabskogo yazika. Kazan, 2009. – P.8

⁶ Chaplina Y.K. O soznatelnom obuchenii inostrannim yazikam v sredney shkole. // Inostr. yaziki v shkole. - 1948. - № 2. - P. 72.

⁷ Raxmanov I.V. O zadachax prepodavaniya inostrannix yazikov v shkole / Izvestiya APN RSFSR. Vip. 32. - M., 1951. - P. 128.

S.S. Artemyeva, M.P. Bazina, Zh.I. Igumnova, and others, developed a system of communicative foreign language teaching that has been successfully used by many foreign language teachers.

Recognized by scholars and researchers as fundamental, the combined method has held a dominant position in foreign language teaching for several decades. E.I. Passov, S.F. Shatilov, G.V. Rotova, N.I. Gez, I.L. Bim, A.A. Leontiev, P.B. Gurvich, and others are proponents of this method. We also believe that there is currently an integration of methods. The effectiveness of a particular method depends on the goals and conditions of teaching, the category of learners, and many other factors⁸.

A retrospective analysis of the evolutionary development of foreign language teaching methods (direct, conscious-comparative, combined) has revealed an insufficient use of elements that activate students' thinking. Problem-based learning contributes to the activation of thinking.

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⁸ Shayxullin T.A., Gazal Ainiya A.N., Obucheniye rechevoy deyatel'nosti arabskogo yazika. Kazan, 2009. – P.13